

PRODUCT DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT: SURVEY ON THE NEED FOR MEDI-PEN

Aisha Abdelaziz, Basma Alraeesi, Shaikha Mohammed, Mzoun Mussabeh, Shamma Omar, Hind Tahnoon, Fedaa Mohammed, Ahmad Mamdouh Akkad

ABSTRACT

Customer needs give rise to concepts that aims to fulfil their targets in a form of product. Product development involves planning, concept development, system-level design, detailed design, testing and refinement, and production ramp-up. This project designed Medi-pen that can help people with Diabetes

INTRODUCTION

Concept or opportunity generation is a process, which is initiated with a set of customer needs and target specifications and results in a variety of product design alternatives. One final design can be selected from these alternatives that are equal parts desired by the customer, viable by the business, and technologically feasible. However, these steps require a highly creative, abstract style of thinking.

The conceptualization phase is one part of the much larger engineering process, and the steps involved in this process include identification of customer needs, clear definition of the problems and objectives at hand, generation of a concept or solution, drafting and the following analysis, detailed designing that can include drawings or sketches, creation of a prototype of the design, testing the prototype and, final delivery of the product. This product planning or conceptualization phase is the first phase in the product development process and helps in the decision making of which product development projects can be initiated or processed further. A more generic take of the product development process involves planning, concept development, system-level design, detailed design, testing and refinement and, production ramp-up.

Generation of opportunities for innovative products requires a rigorous brainstorming session with due consideration to the factors mentioned above. With such a session, the possibility of multiple concepts arises; however, they are filtered, keeping in mind the feasibility of the concept in each step of product planning and development. We conducted a survey specially designed to question the daily struggles faced by individuals, which could be fixed with a new technologically

advanced product. Ideas were then generated by a group discussion based on the responses of the survey. The concepts were then analysed based on technological feasibility and business viability. The few concepts that seemed to pass these criteria were then selected for designing, and samples were drawn up. These samples were then developed into prototypes, and a strict material quality check was undertaken to ensure that the product would successfully fulfil the requirements. After eliminations at each of these steps, the following ideas were selected as possibly successful opportunities.

One of the opportunities we generated was that of a storm proof umbrella. This innovative idea was conceptualized based on customer requirements. One common survey response was frustration with umbrellas that keep blowing inside out and leading to messy days and eventually ending up useless all too soon. Surprising statistics have shown that over 1 billion umbrellas are discarded each, and therefore sustainability was a very significant factor in the selection of this opportunity. This concept also makes a strong statement against pollution by completely eliminating the concept of a throwaway umbrella and introducing a revolutionary lifetime use umbrella. This innovative product can offer a strong and practical design that ensures a mess-free day by protecting people from the heaviest showers, worst storms, and brightest sunshine while also providing style and comfort. The proposed unique design was tested at high wind speeds to ensure that the umbrella would be able to withstand heavy storms. The proposed asymmetrical shape allows the wind to pass around with minimal resistance. Tradition features like lightweight structure, the quick-dry fabric will be maintained while also introducing up to 50-UV sun protection.

The second concept picked by our team was that of a solar-powered smart water geyser. This geyser was designed to cut down on electrical costs while utilizing three alternate resources depending on availability. This innovation has been conceptualized specifically for third-world countries where resources are in scarcity and highly expensive. The resources made available for this product will be solar energy, electrical supply, and gas supply. An application for this product has been specially designed to program the timings during which the geyser will be turned on. This feature will reduce electricity usage, which is regarded as the most expensive resource, and this will only be utilized when no other resource is available.

The third product that has been conceptualized based on multiple survey answers is that of a medi-pen that will be able to record glucose and administer insulin accordingly in the same prick. This product will be designed with strict healthcare regulations and will be designed with special consideration to affordability, as this has been a major issue faced by diabetics.

RWW ANALYSIS

A RWW analysis was conducted for each concept individually. The opportunities were considered to be real breakthroughs with a strong market that can be served with our products as an initial survey has already been conducted to consider popular responses that can be resolved with new technologically advanced products. Inspection of the market size was carried out for each product by generating another survey to assess the popularity or willingness to use each product by the people. A sizeable population was surveyed for every concept. Potential pricing was estimated with regard to production prize, business profits as well as popularity. Availability of technology had already been considered in the designing of the products or prototypes. Only the strongest concepts had been selected for product designing, and a popular innovation was thus guaranteed. The uniqueness of these products would also guarantee a sustainable competitive advantage for these products, along with using high-quality materials at extremely reasonable prices. However, further research needs to be carried out on whether or not the product can be patented. From a

financial perspective, the opportunities definitely seem worth the effort, and the investment could prove to be highly profitable.

MISSION STATEMENTS

Mission Statement for Storm resistant Umbrella

Product description

Storm resistant umbrella for lifetime use.

Benefit Proposition

Guaranteed life time use, comfortable, stylish, light weight and protection from UV rays.

Key business Goals

90 % replacement from all umbrella users, popularity due to high sustainability

Primary Market

Residents of rainy countries.

Secondary Market

All customers requiring umbrella

Assumptions

Need for everyone living in the rain prone areas.

Stakeholders

User, customer and major retailers and manufacturing supply chains.

Mission Statement for Water Geysers

Product description

A programmable/ smart water geysers with multiple resources for residential use

Benefit Proposition

Simple to use, saves energy, cost effective.

Key business Goals

40% gross margin, sizeable margin of profit from mobile application, accepted adaptability of 60% market using geysers

Primary Market

Residential customers

Secondary Market

Big scale production for various industries needing temperature controlled water

Assumptions

Compatible with most existing systems and wiring, application compatible with majority of the mobile models used by people

Stakeholders

User, retailer and production industry and service centre

Mission Statement for Medi-Pen

Product description

Medi-pen for simultaneous glucose check and insulin administration

Benefit Proposition

Simple to use, only one prick, highly affordable

Key business Goals

Introduction of product through all major pharmaceutical companies, high profitability margin (up to 80%)

Primary Market

Diabetic patients

Secondary Market

Hospital admitted patients with high diabetes

Assumptions

Will become the primary source of insulin for diabetic patients, high accuracy of glucose check, FDA approval of product

Stakeholders

Patient, pharmaceutical company, health care practitioners

Customer focus is all about outing the needs of your customers before everything else and enhancing their experience, so there is greater customer satisfaction. In case of a bad experience, more than half the customers switch to a competitor brand or product, and the number goes even higher in case of a second bad experience. Hence it is necessary to get to the depth of the fault and assess what caused the customer to have a bad experience. For this purpose, a customer feedback system that is easily accessible to all should be in place, or a team is set up to reach out to people and record all their grievances. The customers are reached out and their needs recorded into categories of explicit, unfulfilled, and latent needs. Latent needs are those that cannot be fulfilled or satisfied, maybe due to the lack of information.

The needs statement of any product or organization establishes the problem faced and how it will be addressed. It is necessary to use the need statement to reach the ultimate goal of a product. The product should solve the people's issues; only then will it be a successful idea or product.

Our product is a storm-proof umbrella that helps to weather the storm without being affected by it by its unique and aerodynamic design. If it is accurately assessed, there will always be some effect, no matter how hi-tech and storm-proof the umbrella is. Walking through a storm will still have its effect. The team brainstorms how to best deal with the problem without giving any extra expectations. The need statement should be attractive and problem-solving.

For the water geyser, the need statement is the easy availability of water at your preferred temperature. The geyser should be able to meet its need of providing water at different temperatures may it be cold in summers or hot in winters.

The medi-pen for diabetic patients the need statement is to check your glucose levels easily and get a dose of insulin administered according to your required need. A lot of other factors may also

need to be considered here besides just the dose that should be administered. It is necessary to brainstorm for a justifiable relationship between the need statement and accurate specifications for any product before it is launched.

HOQ TABLE

House of Quality is a tool used for defining the relationship between customer desires and the capabilities of the product. It is often presented in the form of a diagram.

HOQ table for medi-pen

Customer Attributes (CAs) \ Functional Requirement (FRs)	Streamlined Appearance	Ergonomic Design	High Density Cell	High Temperature Tolerance Material	Screen	Row Number	Cas Weight
Industrial Feeling	5	3	0	0	3	1	3
Handy operated	0	5	0	0	1	2	1
Long Battery Life	1	0	5	0	0	3	5
Safe	1	0	3	5	0	4	5
Cheap	1	1	3	3	5	5	1
Light	0	0	3	1	0	6	3
Column Number	1	2	3	4	5		

CONCEPT GENERATION

For analysing any product, internal and external researches are carried out. Both have their own pros and cons. For external research, often a third party is hired who is able to give an unbiased view on the product or idea and is the expert on the niche. For all the three ideas, external researches are carried out by hiring companies that have experts in these niches and have ample knowledge to be able to assess fully.

The strength of internal research is that the employees are familiar with the product and the customers and can give an insight into both things. There are through with both the things and know the problems to the depth, but this same advantage can turn into a disadvantage when looking at

products more objectively. The internal employees may at times not be able to view the product from the customer point of view and state their idea as a whole about product and business.

To gather a broader view of the market, it is necessary to do both internal and external research for any product.

The research was done on the components used for making the storm-proof umbrella, the water geysers, and the medi-pen. The components of each should be sustainable, safe, and in line with ergonomic features. The umbrella and medi-pen especially should meet the standards of ergonomic features as they are to be directly used. Different analysis was carried out on them internally by getting detailed feedback from employees. This was done through conducting an external employee survey, so there is no biasness and complete anonymity. Even though it sounds simple but conducting employee surveys that can be actually useful to transform the workplace can be quite tricky. Working with external researchers allows employees to give back honest feedback without the fear of backlash. Surveys are made by specialists to be as engaging and interactive as possible to generate good data for the company. Company management often defines the direction of study, but zero biasness and anonymity are what get the actual credible results that can be used.

Focus groups are another great way to conduct research best internally. Focus groups can start discussions on various arguments and controversial opinions. A candid conversation with a neutral direction is carried out. The employees must feel comfortable in the discussion, and that sometimes means having an external resource that has no connection with them. This kind of research requires a moderator who can lead the discussions and let participants explore their own ideas without any judgment. As the focus group is used to form an opinion about a new product or identify its problems, all the management and the engineers involved should be removed from the discussion if an unbiased outcome is needed.

Customer insights are also looked into depth which is done by internal research as the internal employees have an unrivalled knowledge of their customers with them. Only minute details of customers are known internally and can be analysed in-depth.

CONCEPT SELECTION

Concept screening and scoring are used to take all the designs created and use the decision matrices, which have the selection criteria to help prioritize and choose one single design. This is done by defining the success criteria of each design and then making a decision. By carrying out all the concept screening and scoring, the idea selected is of medi-pen as it has the highest odds and is most likely to be a winning product.

A- Storm-proof umbrella

B- Water Geysers

C- Medi-peN

Concept Screening Matrix for Medi-pen

	CONCEPTS							
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	REF.
Selection Criteria	Cylinders/ Barrels	Rubber Brakes	Dual Plunger Push	Levers	Ratchet	Needle Replacement	Display Screen	Existing Product

Ease of Handling	0	0	0	-	-	+	-	0
Settings Readability	0	-	0	-	-	-	+	0
Glucose Measurement Accuracy	0	-	0	0	+	-	+	0
Dose Administration Accuracy	+	+	0	0	+	0	0	0
Ease of Use	0	+	+	-	0	+	+	0
Durability	+	+	+	+	-	+	0	0
Portability	+	0	-	-	-	+	-	0
Plusses	3	3	2	1	2	4	3	0
Sames	4	2	4	2	1	1	2	0
Minuses	0	2	1	4	4	2	2	0
Net	3	1	1	-3	-2	2	1	
Rank	1	3	4	7	6	2	5	
Continue?	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	

Concept Scoring Matrix

Concepts									
Selection Criteria	Weight	A (reference) Dual Cylinders		B Rubber Brakes		F Needle Replacement		G+ Display Screen	
		Rating	Weighted Score	Rating	Weighted Score	Rating	Weighted Score	Rating	Weighted Score
Ease of Handling	10%	3	0.15	2	0.15	4	0.2	4	0.2
Ease of use	10%	3	0.45	3	0.6	4	0.6	3	0.45
Readability	5%	2	0.2	2	0.3	5	0.5	5	0.5
Glucose Measurement Accuracy	25%	4	0.75	3	0.5	2	0.5	3	0.75
Dose Administration Accuracy	25%	5	0.75	3	0.1	4	0.6	3	0.45
Durability	10%	2	0.6	2	0.2	2	0.4	2	0.4
Portability	15%	4	0.3	2	0.3	3	0.3	3	0.3
Total Score		3.2		2.15		3.10		3.05	
Rank		1		4		2		3	
Continue?		Yes		No		No		No	

CONCEPT SURVEY

The team selected a targeted segment of society that is the diabetic population and surveyed them. They were randomly picked, and a target audience was chosen. Their views on the medi-pen were recorded, and whether or not they faced any problems while checking their glucose levels daily and the administration of doses was also recorded. The survey This recorded data was collected and analysed to reach a more informed opinion about the market needs. The chosen audience for survey should be random from different areas, of different age groups, different gender and class.

CONCEPT ARCHITECTURE

The medi-pen was designed keeping in mind all the things required for it to be effective and safe.

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